

ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL DIVERSITY IN ENGLISH TEXTBOOKS AT SECONDARY LEVEL IN PUNJAB: A SOCIO-SEMIOTIC STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Culture is a very important aspect of Identity. It is a versatile term and has many different definitions and descriptions. Cultural representation in the textbooks plays a very crucial role in learning and developing inter-cultural competence in the students. However, it is very important to understand different aspects of written text and visuals in the textbooks. Cultural representation in the textbooks is widely researched area. A number of researches have claimed that there is an imbalance in the representation of cultural diversity throughout many regions in the world. However, none of the studies have explained the portrayal of cultural diversity in English textbooks at secondary level in Punjab developed by Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board. The present study fills this existing gap. The whole text of secondary level English textbooks has been examined. The qualitative descriptive design along with purposive sampling is used in the study. Grade 9th and 10th English textbooks of Punjab are taken as samples. To examine the cultural diversity in the textbooks, Yuen's (2012) analytical framework is employed along with multi-modal discourse analysis. There are 5 aspects of Yuen's model that are employed for analysis of data. The results show that there is an imbalance in the textbook, with grade 9th textbook focusing more on Islamic aspects of culture and the grade 10th textbook portraying the dominance of foreign culture. However, there should be culturally responsive educators who incorporate culturally responsive teaching practices in order to give value to the diverse cultural perspectives.

Keywords: Cultural diversity, Inclusivity, English textbooks, Social Semiotics.

Introduction:

English is a global language and has been taught in Pakistan even before the country's inception (Hafeez & Asif, 2010). The use of English as global language and teaching English at various level with the help of English textbooks plays an important role in acquisition of both cultural and linguistic knowledge. Language and Culture are tightly connected with each other and thought to be co-constitutive. English textbooks should

incorporate cultural and intercultural aspects so that linguistic and cultural competence can be enhanced. Language and culture are chiefly the aspects that are progressively more found at the core of development in Applied Linguistics. It provides insight into the nature of language acquisition.

Hall (2013) gives the view on nature of language and culture by focusing on the use of language in real world circumstances and how language aids

in identifying cultures. Culture is such an important aspect of language that it is not possible to teach language devoid of cultural integration. Hence, portrayal of Cultural diversity in English textbooks must be ensured to develop cultural and linguistic competence in students. English has become academic and occupational language throughout the world and it's necessary to access the opportunities crossing the linguistic barriers.

Textbooks implicitly and explicitly conduct cultural values, expansion of knowledge and student's perspective of themselves and other person's (Ndura 2004). Culture and Language are undoubtedly very closely related to each other (Baker 2012, Scarino 2013). Learning language is not only about learning an expression but a part of culture that is depicted in language. A person who learns language without learning culture is at risk of becoming fluent fool (Bennet 2003). Culture with no doubt an indispensable aspect of language has always remain debatable. Due to central role of English textbooks in language education, English textbooks has been a subject of investigation for the content related to culture present in the textbooks.

It is widely recognized that English Language Education should not only lead students to be known of communicative skills but also provide sufficient knowledge of Culture as well(Baker 2012, Byram 1997). Cultural awareness is actually very important to avoid misunderstanding and mis-communication (Chlopek 2008). Culture is crucial element in English textbooks (Tajeddin and Teimounezhad, 2015).English teaching and learning is encouraged not only to encourage culture of English speaking countries but also for intercultural perspectives (Baker 2012, Bennet 2003, Byram 1997). The term culture actually develop the base of intercultural communication. Social semiotics is advanced branch in linguistics introduced by Michael Halliday in 1978. It is mainly concerned with relationship between meaning maker and meaning making. It is an advanced and comprehensive field in linguistics. It provides understanding of modes of communication (Bezemer & Jewitt, 2009). It has mode, sign, interest, meaning and other such

factors as key notions. In social semiotics, the issue of education and literacy have been discussed in comprehensive matter. At the same time, it is also advancing field (Gualberto & Kress). Socio-semiotic has been implemented as an enhanced technique in research (Benatta bou, 2021). " How meaning and form have been brought together in a relation motivated by interest of the meaning maker" (Bezemer & Kress, 2008, p 170). It also discusses means of communication. Social semiotics is qualitative in nature, in depth analysis of the text, pictures, recordings and documents.

Hassan and Raddatz in (2008) conducted a research in which they compared the affective, cognitive as well as procedural points of English secondary textbooks taught in Syria and also in Germany. The Results has shown that the Syrian English data have developed the balance of three major aspects, however English textbooks of Germany only emphasized affective as well as procedural aspects of the UK. Garcia in (2005) conducted the research in which he deeply examined English textbooks' cultural elements and noted out cultural biasness in cultural presentation of Spanish English textbooks. They were actually in favor of target language and its cultural values and traditions.

In Asia, Shin et al. (2011) conducted the study and compared the aspects of cultural representation and the levels of the cultural representation in all seven series of 25 of the total English textbooks in several countries of Asia. They take the notice and concluded the domination of the Inner Circle and its cultural aspects in all the examined textbooks. Yuen in (2011) conducted a research in order to investigate the cultural material of two English course books in the Hong Kong secondary grades and results shown that cultures of English countries were more dominant as usual and the African cultures in comparability were more under-represented and repressed. hence lot of the studies have highlighted cultural materials in English textbooks in all the different areas, Cortazzi and Jin (1999) maintained that additional research with a more reflective attitude toward cultural content and methodology is needed in various countries to meet the goal of

improving cultural awareness from the EIL perspective. Textbooks should embrace a variety of voices, views, and sections from different cultural credentials.

Culture:

Culture is the multifaceted whole that contains belief, acquaintance, art, law, tradition and other habits and abilities attained by man as a member. Culture contain products of all experiences either less or more ordered that are shaped and learned by individuals. It is basically indoctrination of brain that splits one group from the members of other group. Ethos is always demonstrated at different layers of depth that includes values, observable artifacts and basic underlying assumptions.

It is imperative to delve into the underlying assumptions, which are typically unconscious but actually determine how the members of the group perceive, think and feel. Such assumptions are themselves learned responses that originated as espoused values. But, as a value leads to a behavior, that comportment begins to solve the problem which prompted it in the first place. The value is gradually transformed into an underlying assumption about how things really are. As the assumption is progressively taken for granted, it drops out of sentience.

Types of culture

Culture is the set of ideas and beliefs that is broadly divided into two main types' i.e material and non-material culture that represents tangible and physical aspects of society. Material culture represents artifacts and physical objects while non-material culture represents the beliefs, ideas and values. However there are subsets that are high culture and low culture. High culture is basically crafted by an educated class. Low culture is basically formed by daily actions and traditions. [Schein].

Material Culture

This refers to the artifacts and includes the physical objects that is used and valued by society. It includes the technology, clothing, housing and art. Material culture is the combination of products and the monuments including the

architectural objects, the textile and clothing, tools and the technological products, the icons as well as the symbols. Tangible culture actually provides an insight into their cultural values of the region and makes the cultural values prominent in the world.

Non-Material culture

It includes the intangible aspects of culture for instance values, beliefs, social roles, language, symbols and norms. The non-material culture includes the practices and the perspectives. These are the abstract cultural portrayal. It includes the norms and the customs that can be unwritten rules or law, verbal and non-verbal cues, patterns of social organization, ideas and beliefs that can be either individual or collective. Non-material culture basically influences the patters of peoples thinking and the perceptions of their individual or collective experiences.

Cultural Inclusivity in Textbooks:

The portrayal of cultural diversity in language textbooks promotes equity and inclusion. Incorporating diverse culture in the textbooks promotes inclusive teaching practices, introducing multicultural literature, integrating cultural competence training and reflecting on inclusive culture are strategic plans for implementing cultural diversity in textbooks. Textbooks play a vital role in shaping young minds, and ensuring they reflect cultural diversity is crucial for fostering inclusivity and understanding. While efforts to incorporate diverse perspectives are increasing, research indicates that cultural bias and stereotypical representations can still be found in some materials.

Weninger & Kiss (2013) argued that the students' comprehension on the understanding of culture was instructed and facilitated via texts, pictorial forms, and activities. It also helps to get cultural education with the help of images in a learning classroom. In the view of McGrath (2014) that is cited in Faris, textbooks must have cultural content. Textbooks always play an integral part in providing students beneficial meaning about new and different cultural values of expressions and cultural sameness. Adding to it, Tomalin (2008)

argued the point that culture is basically a fifth language skill that comes after speaking, writing, listening, and reading. as well, teaching culture in English textbooks should take in account cultural information, cultural values and norms, cultural heritage, and cultural adeptness, as its cited in (Ikromah, 2018).

Problem Statement:

The utilization of textbooks is central to any educational course at least, in a traditional sense and within the bounds of present technology and practice. Culture and language are interdependent hence there should be portrayal of cultural Inclusivity in order to develop cultural and linguistic competence. The portrayal of cultural inclusivity in language textbooks promotes equity and inclusion.

Punjab Being diverse in culture, the lack of representation and the promotion of cultural inclusivity in the English textbooks at secondary level in Punjab is the problem statement addressed in the study. Lacking cultural diversity in the textbook result in perpetuating the cultural stereotypes and the cultural biases. It places negative impact on the student's attitudes and their perception toward diverse culture. The problem statement is actually inferred from the literature review that sheds light on the significance of promoting cultural diversity in the textbook.

Research question:

Global researches have shown that the textbooks often reflect the dominant culture and there is represent representation of the minorities as well as the other cultures. Pakistan is actually multicultural country with diverse cultural values and a rich cultural heritage. Punjab is most populous and culturally rich province of Punjab. Its home to diverse cultural aspects leading to unique cultural significance of the province. However due to growing concern of inter cultural competence in the world there is a need to analyze the cultural diversity in the textbooks of secondary level in Punjab. Keeping in view the need of hour the overarching research question of this research is:

1. How much is cultural diversity portrayed in English textbooks at secondary level in Punjab?

Research Objectives:

Cultural diversity refers to multiple cultures existing in society. As far the portrayal of cultural diversity is concerned in English textbooks, it is the variety of cultural content that exist in the English textbooks of secondary level in Punjab. The cultural diverse curriculum results in enhanced competence in the students and leads to exposure to several cultures. It encompasses the difference in beliefs, customs and values as well as in language and artistic expressions.

Cultural Inclusivity is mainly manifested through linguistic diversity, religious pluralism, and cultural traditions and opposed to monoculture. Cultural diversity in English textbooks refers to incorporation of diverse perspectives, experiences, values into educational material and more equitable and inclusive environment. The portrayal of cultural diversity in English textbooks involves valuing the legitimacy and acknowledging different cultures. The multicultural textbooks reflects multicultural reality of today's society. Hence, the study was undertaken to analyze the portrayal of cultural diversity in English Textbooks of secondary level in Punjab.

Scope of the study:

Textbooks play an important role in education. They facilitate both teachers and students. Language of the textbooks as well as the content included also play a significant role. The content written in textbook shapes one's thoughts and beliefs. The research highlights the importance of cultural inclusivity in the English textbooks. The inclusion of cultural content will give exposure to the multi-cultural globalized world. Cultural diversity in the content should obligatory be included and integrated into English textbooks in order to exacerbate Cultural awareness in the students and the ways to conduct intercultural communication properly. As we know intercultural communication has become most demanding and needed skills in the present times, English textbooks must be developed in a

way to provide intercultural challenges that allows the students to discuss ahead their native and other cultures during learning English (Nomnian, 2013a).

The research has significant implications in fostering an equitable and more engaging learning environment. The selected research problem will help to make the fact prominent that cultural inclusivity in the English textbooks will enhance intercultural communicative competence. The cultural inclusivity appreciate diverse perspectives and challenge stereotypes. By inclusion of cultural content in the textbooks there is promotion of respect, empathy and understanding to globalized world. The study will contribute to the existing literature on the cultural diversity and inclusion in the English textbooks of secondary level in Punjab as well as highlights the significance of promoting intercultural competence. Finally the current study provides the guideline and recommendations to the textbook developers, policy makers and teachers to promote more inclusive and diverse cultural values.

Literature review:

Culture is basically that complex whole that includes belief, knowledge, art, law, custom and other habits and capabilities acquired by man as a member. Culture contain derivatives of all experiences either less or more organized that are created and learned by individuals. Culture is basically programming of brain that separates one group from the members of other group. Culture is always manifested at different layers of depth that includes values, observable artifacts and basic underlying assumptions.

English Textbooks in Pakistan:

In Pakistan, textbooks in English language enjoy prestigious status due to several reasons. English textbooks in Pakistan and other countries have been studied various time for content analysis purpose and cultural inclusivity. Aftab (2012) in thesis work explored English textbooks of Punjab. However it is very significant for the cultural diversity to exist in the textbooks. First of all it helps to promote intercultural understanding as well as appreciation that

enables students to create deeper understanding of the diverse traditions and cultures the world.

It fosters tolerance and empathy that helps the students to appreciate the experiences and perspectives of others. Cultural diversity in the textbooks promotes cultural and social cohesion, the aspect of national unity and sense of shared citizenship and belonging. Textbooks are the crucial mode to shape students cognition for the importance of cultural diversity. Textbooks can either provide a congestive and narrow perspective go the students or bring them out in extensive platform of intercultural experiences. In Punjab, Pakistan the textbooks plays a significant role in shaping students understanding of their cultural values and heritage by portraying the cultural practices and perspectives. However it is very important to examine the textbooks regarding the cultural diversity and its representation.

Context of the Study:

Punjab is the most populous and culturally diverse province of the Pakistan. It is a region diverse in culture with a versatile heritage. Punjab province has a distinctive cultural identity that is designed and shaped by its historical perspective, traditional aspects, and norms values. Punjab province is a center to diverse ethnic groups, linguistic element and religious aspects including Punjabis, Christians, Sikhs, and other communities. Punjab has a vast history of cultural interchange and diversity, along with diversity of cultures and civilizations that is having an influence on development throughout the centuries.

DAHMARDEH, University of Tehran, MAHDIKHANI, International Kish Campus, University of Tehran, Iran in 2025 conducted a research after the revised Educational strategy of Iran in 1979. The study analyzes the cultural representation in locally published and internationally published English textbooks in Iran. By inculcating mixed method approach and by applying Byram and Morgan Framework 58 textbooks were selected by purposive sampling. Quantitative content analysis helped in analyzing the frequencies and types of cultural elements that exist in the textbooks. However on the other

hand qualitative analysis helps to highlight the themes of cultural content occurring in the textbooks. The results indicate that the locally published textbooks inculcate more cultural content as compared to internationally published textbooks. The results indicate that there was balanced cultural representation in the local textbooks including both source and target culture. However the results indicate the importance of incorporating multiculturalism in the textbooks that in turn will enhance the cultural competence of the students.

MOSTAFA, Khulna University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh Rubaiyat JAHAN, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh conducted a research focusing on the representation of cultural aspects in higher secondary English textbooks in Bangladesh focusing on the diversity of the culture portrayed in the textbooks. The sample was the two English textbooks of higher secondary level. The research work employs the content analysis along with qualitative descriptive research design. The results of the analysis show that there is under presentation of African and Asian culture however there is over presentation of western culture. The results conclude that there is dominance of the western culture in the textbooks creating an imbalance in the books. However along with it, the Asian and African women are portrayed commonly and their works are considered mundane however the western women are presented more gracefully. However the broader representation of the international culture can help Bangladeshi students to become global speakers.

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Keles and Yazan (2023) conducted a Diachronic content analysis on how cultures are represented in NHE across its five editions. Kachru's model of concentric circles for data collection was used and categorized as practice, person, perspective and products. The analysis of the data concluded that there was more representation of European and American Cultures and there was suppressed representation of other cultures in almost all editions of NHE textbooks.

Theoretical framework:

Social semiotics was introduced by Michael Halliday in 1978 and its main concern is with meaning makers and meaning making it also discusses modes of communication. Social semiotics is qualitative in nature it analyses text pictures recordings and documents intensely. Different novel versions of social semiotics have

been emerged after Halliday's publication of language as social semiotics Today social semiotics is fully developed branch itself proposed by Michael Halliday. It focused on meaning making and meaning makers in every aspect whether it is visual gesture or verbal. Semiotic expands its context by implication of society to language and communications. Signs are not in isolation but they refer to society and of course it differs society to society and person to person. Halliday first used term social semiotics as the title of his book language as social semiotics. In his book he showed opposition toward traditional separation between language and society. Ultimately it broadens the narrow focus on written language. It ascribes meaning to all modes of communication including image, writing, typography and layout. It treats signs of any kind as reflecting the interest of makers of these signs. From a social semiotic perspective visual images as any other form of communication may reflect a multitude of hidden ideologies social and cultural values and power relations in the 2nd order representation. The focus of this study is to analyze the inclusivity of cultural content in English textbooks at secondary level in Punjab. Culture is crucial construct of the society. The present research is set on the theoretical grounds of Socio-Semiotic Theory given by Michael Halliday. It was given by Michael Halliday on 1960s and state that Language plays a functional role to convey meaning through various modes at contextual level.

Research methodology:

Research methodology is the backbone of whole research project. It incorporates research approach, data collection methods, sampling and analysis processes as well. Furthermore all of these constitutes are discussed as well as justified in research methodology section. Kothari argues that the importance of research methodology by mentioning it in absolute systematic procedure to solve research problems that exist in any study. Methodology act like a science and researcher himself is responsible for applying techniques and procedures with logic.

Research design:

In order to analyze the cultural diversity in English textbooks, qualitative research design will be incorporated. Multimodal discourse analysis of the textbook corpora will be done. Selected textbooks will be analyzed by multimodal approach and the data will be analyzed by multimodal means to understand the cultural diversity in the textbooks. Multimodal discourse analysis is a field that studies how meaning is created through the combination of various modes of communication, going beyond the traditional focus on language alone. It examines how text, images, sounds, gestures, and other semiotic resources interact to convey meaning. This approach recognizes that meaning is often not solely conveyed through words, but also through visual, auditory, and spatial elements.

Data collection and sampling:

Data has been collected from the English textbook of secondary level of 9th and 10th grade that is published by PCTB. The English textbook have been taken as a sample. In the sample size all the images and text that are culture oriented were included. The tool of the research was textbook. As far the sampling is concerned the sampling type was non probability purposive sampling. It is also known as judgmental and selective sampling. Benattabou (2021) states that purposive sampling is a procedure where researcher already has some pre-fixed criteria for sampling.

Data analysis procedure:

The data is analyzed by using multi-modal discourse analysis and by analytical framework of Yuen (2008). The English textbooks of secondary level in Punjab are analyzed on the six basic grounds. Yuen's model of analysis is based on the four pillars of the culture that includes Products, persons, perspectives and personalities however the pictures and the places are included in the analysis by using a multi-modal discourse analysis. The text of the both textbooks is taken as the sample of the study. All the activities, side information and the reading text is analyzed using a multi-modal discourse analysis. The analysis of the data is set on the theoretical

grounds of socio-semiotic Cultural theory. The cultural aspects are categorized into six each leading to the collection and categorization of the relevant data from the sample.

Results:

Products:

Cultural products are goods and services that embody and express the values, beliefs, and practices of a specific culture. They can include a wide range of items, from artistic creations like music, literature, and visual art, to tangible objects like clothing, food, and architecture, as well as intangible elements like traditions, rituals, and social customs.

Food items includes Kiwi that is fruit item that's mentioned in grade 9 English textbooks that has its cultural origin from New Zealand, Pizza that is the food item from Italian cultural context. Jiaozi is a type of Chinese food; dumplings that are eaten on Chinese New Year Nian GAO. Nian GAO is traditional Chinese food that is specifically cooked on Chinese New Year. Tanguan is Chinese dessert that is representing Chinese culture. However, Technological inventions includes Fax machine and Symbols include Polecat that is a type of fish that specifically exist in Europe region and North Africa. Polka is aesthetic dance and music that has been originated in bohemia. Pollack

is the food item that is specifically eaten in North Africa hence portraying its culture through the food items. Daffodils. A symbolism of spring and is usually a symbol of new start and joy in eater hence portraying the culture of Christianity centered countries. Messiah that is originated from Hebrew language is usually a savior and leader and is culturally representing Christianity and the Judaism making it worldwide cultural symbols for the people belonging to Christianity and Judaism. Sahaba are companions of holy prophet p.b.u.h and they were the people interacting with the pagan to make them Muslim. They symbolizes the Islamic culture. Black stone is very important relic in Islam that is located in Makah in Saudi Arabia that is portraying Islamic culture in the textbook. The black stone represents historical event in the history of Islam. Chinese lunar calendar. It's deeply embedded in Chinese culture that greatly influence traditional

festivals and follow the sun and moon cycles in order to relate to the fate of the people. Horse riding is representation of Mongolia that's called the land of horses represents its culture through its national game horse riding that's also played in several other countries in the world. Rugby is the national game of New Zealand that symbolizes discipline and teamwork. Tennis that has been originated from England and is now cultural manifestation of the European countries.

Persons:

Cultural persons actually refers to the shared personality attributes and traits, values and norms and their behavioral patterns that are characteristics of a particular culture or a particular society. The traits are shaped by cultural values, influencing how an individual think or feel.

Holy prophet (P.B.U.H). Hazrat Muhammad (S.A.W) is last prophet of Allah almighty. The name of holy personality is repeated for many times in both textbooks emphasizing Islamic culture and the norms and traditions that are related to Islam and Islamic countries. Walid bin yazid was caliph of Umayyad dynasty who ruled Syria for years Hazrat Gabriel (A.S). Hazrat Gabriel is messenger angel in Islam who's known for bringing divine messages to prophets. Hazrat jibreel is most known for the revelations like Quran. The holy personality is discussed in the textbooks portraying the Islamic spiritual values and highlighting the significance of Islamic culture in the textbooks. Hazrat Abu talib was the leader of Banu Hashmi tribe in mecca, a clan of Qureshi tribe that actually exist in hijazi region of Arab peninsula. The personality is manifesting the cultural values of Islam and is showing the sacredness. Hazrat Ayesha (R.A) is third wife of holy prophet (P.B.U.H) and daughter of Hazrat Abu Bakar Siddique (R.A).

Hazrat Asma (R.A) is regarded as symbol of courage and bravery in Islam. Hazrat Abu Bakar Siddique (R.A). Hazrat Abu Bakar was closest companion and father in law of holy prophet. The holy personality is discussed portraying the international culture in the textbook. Abu Jehl is portraying international culture as he was prominent opponent of Islam in early times.

Ashfaq Ahmad is military broadcaster, playwright and poet. He has been a very important figure in military literature. Walter Scott is known Scottish play write, a novelist and a poet. The writing of Scott are representing the culture and heritage of Scotland. The Scottish Play write is portraying the International native culture of Scotland making the textbooks diverse is its cultural content. The personality showcases the cultural identity, the historical context of Scotland as well as promotes cultural understanding.

Michael Hart. Michael H. Hart is an American Astrophysics and science writer. William words worth, an English poet was major figure of romantic era. He was the resident of Cumberland, England.. The personality is portraying the international culture in the textbook. Robert Frost an English American poet who is reflecting the cultural values and perceptions of American Civilization. The personality is reflection of existence of International aspects in the textbooks. W.H Davies a famous English poet is representation of cultural diversity and inclusivity in the textbooks. Earnest Hemingway. A renowned novelist, story writer and journalist is one of the important literary figure who belongs to Chicago. Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali is most important personality in the history of the military. The heroic personality is representing the culture of military and role that is played by Quaid-e-Azam in shaping the cultural values of military. In the chapter 2 of IX grade textbook, there are several Military personalities who were highlighted referring back to separation of sub-continent and the circumstances of separation.. Captain Muhammad Sarwar, Captain Muhammad Tufail, Major Aziz Bhatti, Captain Rashid Minhas, Major Akram, Major Shabir Sharif, Muhammad Mehfoz, Havaladar Lalak Jan and Captain Karnal Sher Khan all are discussed for getting the highest military award that is called Nishan e Haider hence representing the Pakistani national culture. Eduard Von Hartmann, Lyndon B. Johnson, Hellen Keller, Anne Sullivan, William Edward Hickson, Charles Dickens, Sultan Ahmad I, Mehmet Aga, Usama Bin Zaid, Hazrat Ali (R.A), Hazrat Muawia and Hazrat Umar (R.A).

Places

Cultural places are the cultural heritages that are famous for their cultural, architectural and archeological significance. Byzantine Church, Blue Mosque, Makah, Kabah, Arabian Peninsula, Medina, Hajia Sofia mosque, Ukaz, Turkey, Tuscumbia, Portsmouth England, San Francisco, Minar-e-Pakistan, Wagah Border are the famous cultural places that are represented in the textbooks.

Perspectives:

Cultural perspectives are diverse and distinctive viewpoints that are actually designed and shaped by individual's cultural background, influencing their values, behaviors and their view point about the world. Islamic perspective of Tauheed, Islamic perspective on Prophetic Revelations, Islamic perspective of Nabuwat, Islamic perspective of Arab Conquest, Perspective of women's role in spreading Islam, Holy Prophets (P.B.U.H) Perspective on decision making, Quaid's ideological perspective on separate homeland for Muslims, Islamic perspective of Eid-ul-Fitr as celebratory reward after Ramadan, Islamic perspective on sacredness of Arabia. Arabia has been perceived as symbol of sacredness for the Muslims, Islamic perspective of justice, Global perspective of drugs addiction, Tobin Colin perspective of importance of literature, Chinese cultural perspective on New Year celebrations. Chinese perceive New Year as a symbol of new beginning. They perceive New Year and its celebrations as the symbol of new beginning. They wear red dresses on New Year that shows good luck and fortune. However specific dishes mostly eight or nine in quantity are cooked on the New Year, International perspective on civic sense.

Practices:

Cultural practices are tangible and observable ways a group of people share ideas, values and traditions. The cultural practices encompasses a wide range of activities that ranges from daily behavior to specified rituals.

Practice of saying Assalam-u-Alaikum, Practice of saying Hi/Hello, Practice of Namaz and Ablution, Practice of reciting holy Quran,

Chinese Practice of cooking eight or nine dishes on New Year, Chinese perspective of giving money in red envelopes to children. It also includes the Practice of flag raising in Pakistan on 14th August. In western culture good morning and good after noon are usually used as wishing the good time. The practice is represented in the textbook that represents the western cultural practices that makes them significant and distinctive from others. Practice of performing hajj is Islamic practice and traditional value that shows sacredness of kabah. In this religious practice, Muslims pilgrims to Makah and perform

religious practices there. It's a major part of Islamic culture throughout the world.

Pictures:

Cultural pictures actually refer to the images that basically represent as well as depict the aspects of the specific cultural values that include the people, daily life practices, customs, traditional approaches, architecture, and moral beliefs. These can be photographs, illustrations, as well as symbolic representations which aims to provide an insights into a specific societal values and cultural practices. These pictures can be utilized as document to understand and communicate the aspects of the specific culture.

Figure 1: The Chinese Dragon Head

Figure 2: The care and medical treatment of the patient as well as the scarf on the head presenting Pakistani culture.

Figure 3: Wall of China and the representation of over-population

Conclusion:

The results have highlighted many important cultural aspects that are lacking in the textbooks. Authors of the textbooks have tried to develop a balance in the cultural representation but the lack of cultural diversity and inclusivity is still prevailing in the textbooks. Multimodal dimensions that are integrated have revealed several the imbalance in the representation of indigenous and foreign cultures. The results of the study has revealed that both textbooks have presented variety of cultural aspects i-e products, persons, places, perspectives and practices. Practices and persons are portrayed in the textbooks without illustrations. Therefore it results in a difficulty for the students to develop understanding about those cultural values. The results have revealed that the English textbooks lack the proper representation of national culture. The cultural representation at national level is limited to regional identities. It fails to capture the richness of Pakistani national culture (Ali Furqan, Imran Nazeer, 2023). The text is lacking cultural balance that is needed to fit in multi-cultural environment. Persons, products and places are tangible cultural aspects that are actually apparent and exclusive cultural values that students can perceive easily (Lee, 2009). Moran, 2001 has suggested that persons should be portrayed widely in the textbooks because these are model representation of cultures. However the textbooks are showing imbalance regarding the representation of cultural personalities. Practices and perspectives on the other hand are intangible cultural aspects that portrays the daily life values of specific cultures. In the textbook there is an imbalance in representation of these cultural aspects.

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